

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW THE KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE
REGARDING DONATION OF ORGANS IN LAHORE. A
COMMUNITY BASED STUDY****Dr Hafiz Umer Farooq¹, Dr Robina Naheed², Dr Raima Asif³**¹ Assistant Professor, Community Medicine, Sheikh Zayed Medical College, Rahim Yar Khan² Assistant Professor, Community Medicine, Women Medical College, Abbottabad³ Foundation University Medical College Islamabad**Abstract:****Objective:** The purpose of this analysis was to evaluate knowledge and attitudes and to know statistics about public attentiveness of organ donation.**Study Design:** A Cross-sectional Study.**Place and Duration:** In general population of Lahore division and in community medicine department of Services Hospital Lahore for one year duration from May 2018 to May 2019.**Methods:** Participants were assessed through a face-to-face survey. The questionnaire includes variables related to attitude and knowledge towards donation of organs.**Conclusion:** Total 420 people participated; 25 of them rejected to join the study, so 395 total people participated in the analysis. 18 to 27 years was the average age of about 77.5% of the subjects. Above fifty percent of the subjects were students and (51.1%) were women. Our outcomes signpost that there is insufficient information among the over-all people in 25.9%. In 75.2% of them have positive attitude toward donation of organs. The participants knew about "Kidney" could be donated from the media. About 43.80% of the participants did not know the concept of donation of organ in their religion. 57.2% of subjects were in favour of organ donation.**Key words:** General population, Organ donation, Sensitization, Knowledge.**Corresponding author:****Dr Hafiz Umer Farooq,**

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Please cite this article in press Hafiz Umer Farooq et al., *Study to know the knowledge and attitude regarding donation of organs in lahore. A community based study.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(07).

INTRODUCTION:

Six thousands patients every year wait for donation of organ and expire. Providing a name on the waiting list means there is chance of only 10-30% that still not receiving the transplant¹. This is due to the inadequacy of transplant organs in the world²⁻³. Organ donation is an essential component of transplantation⁴. One of the main problems that contribute to the shortage of organs is due to public qualities such as legends, misunderstanding and misinterpreted religious decrees⁵. Many earlier analysis have shown that attitudes and knowledge play an important part in organ donation proportions. The global knowledge incidence for donation of organ ranges from 61% to 86%. This variation is different from religious and cultural beliefs⁶. The USA revealed that 89% of the population has organ donation knowledge. In contrast, in Bursa study revealed that in Turks only 60% were conscious of donation of organ⁷. It is reported that gender, age, educational level and socioeconomic status have an effect on the correct boldness of organ donation; religion, ethics and culture are also influential factors⁸. In recent years, the organ failure burden is increasing, limited research has been done in developing countries and inadequacy of health system is the main hurdle. In Pakistan, 15,000 people are enlist for a liver or heart transplantation⁹. Only 2 studies have been done on information, practice and attitude on organ donation¹⁰. In a tertiary hospital, one study was done and the other is focused on the general population.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This Cross-sectional Study was held in general population of Lahore division and in community medicine department of Services Hospital Lahore for one year duration from May 2018 to May 2019. In this study, non-probable sampling method was used. The participants were informed about the questionnaire and provided sufficient information about the tenacity of the analysis. 385 people sample size was calculated with 95% confidence level and a sampling error of 5%, assuming 50% prevalence for organ donation. All adults of both sexes over 18 years of age were interrogated after knowledgeable consent. Those having no knowledge of organ donation were debarred.

Through a validated questionnaire; Information was recorded from previous data. The attitude and knowledge of the participants were assessed through a face-to-face survey.

The information of the participants was measured with questions about "organ donation term", "body recognition, donation in life", organ donation in religion and organ donation risks to life.

By SPSS version 18.0, Statistical analysis Data were analysed. Frequencies, descriptive statistics and averages were evaluated as appropriate. To evaluate the relationships; Fisher's exact test and Chi-square test were used. P values <0.05% were recorded.

RESULTS:

Approximately 420 people, twenty five of whom rejected to contribute, were approached, so 395 total participants gave their consent, completed the questionnaire, and were therefore selected.

In about 77.5% of all subjects, 18 to 27 years was the age range. The majority of the respondents were students (51.1%) and the women who participated in the survey ruled 217 (55%).

Information Then we asked questions about organ donation.

• What was your information source about donation of organ?

23.40% marked internet and 27% choose television. 3.30% were recognized by radio (Figure 1).

• What is meant by donation of organ? (62.8%) 248 supposed that the term donation of organ meant "tissue removal for transplantation from the human body". 88 (22.3%) answered the correct "All of the above" option. 21 (5.32%) knew that it was a tissue extraction from the human body."

• What are the reasons for organ donation? 81.8% said it was "done to save someone's life". 9.9% of the population answered "For money" and 5.6% of the selected population responded "For compassion / sympathy".

• Which body part can be given?

"Kidney" could be given by 29.90%. Eye donation was known by 21.80%, but skin donation was known by 4.80%. Knowledge score among the participants there was low information about 395 participants (25.8%). There was no noteworthy relationship between knowledge level and gender (p = 0.450), age (p = 0.434), marital status (p = 0.467)

and occupation ($p = 0.053$). Particulars are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Knowledge score of organ donation by demographic variables

Demographic variables	Knowledge score of organ donation				p-value
	Inadequate knowledge	%	Adequate knowledge	%	
Age					
18–27	231	75.5	75	24.5	0.412
28–37	56	70.9	23	29.1	
38–45	6	60.0	4	40	
Gender					
Male	131	73.6	47	26.4	0.450
Female	162	74.7	55	25.3	
Occupation					
Student	160	79.2	42	20.8	0.053
Employed	106	67.9	50	32.1	
Unemployed	27	73	10	27	
Marital status					
Single	227	74.4	78	25.6	0.467
Married	66	73.3	24	26.7	
Religion					
Muslim	283	74.3	98	25.7	0.042*
Hindu	9	90.0	1	10.0	
Christian	1	25.0	3	75.0	

* Cell proportion was >20%

Attitude

- Donated own organs.

106 (26.8%) populations agreed I want to donate to the relatives, the persons who think organs never be donated were 87 (22%), whereas 33 (8.4%) said they absolutely want to give organs regardless of the conditions.

- Subsidies for donations in religion.

Most of the people did not know that their religion allowed donation of organs about 173 (43.8%). Donated organs can be abused or mistreated.

- Who wants to donate their organs?

227 (57.5%) donated to the "Family Member", 157 (39.7%) donated to everyone, and 3 (0.8%) donated to "Foreigners".

- An important factor when making a donation.

175 people (44.3%) will make a donation to one person. The health position of the recipients was important is mentioned by 114 (28.9%). The 73 (18.5%) of subjects said guarantee of respectful organs for treatment would motivate them, while 13 (3.3%) stated that the recipient religion is very important.

- Approval for living donors.

The "Donor" should give consent was marked by 228 (57.72%) of people and consent was given by 114 (28.86%) families. The doctors should give their consent was marked by 38 (9.62%).

- Post-mortem approval

“While (58.9%) 233 thought that their families would have the right to give consent, 93 (23.54%) chose “Nobody, and 25 (6.33%) chose “Doctor”.

Table 2 Attitude score of organ donation by demographic variables

Demographic variables	Attitude score of organ donation				p-value
	Inadequate knowledge	%	Adequate knowledge	%	
Age					
18–27	72	23.5	234	76.5	0.549
28–37	23	29.1	56	70.9	
38–45	3	30	7	70	
Gender					
Male	53	29.8	125	70.2	0.026
Female	45	20.7	172	79.3	
Occupation					
Student	41	20.3	161	79.7	0.049
Employed	49	31.4	107	68.6	
Unemployed	8	21.6	29	78.4	
Marital status					
Single	74	24.3	231	75.7	0.368
Married	24	26.7	66	73.3	
Religion					
Muslim	96	25.2	285	74.8	0.478*
Hindu	2	20.0	8	80	
Christian	0	0	4	100	

* Cell proportion was > 20%

DISCUSSION:

The purpose of this analysis was to evaluate knowledge and attitudes and to know statistics about public attentiveness of organ donation. Our results exposed very interesting opinions. Our analysis showed that the population (25.8%) had sufficient knowledge about organ donation and that only 22.3% knew the importance of organ donation¹¹. As in the previous study, however, the information showed (60%) prevalence among the people. A study among university students in Nadu Tamil showed that the results (28.9%) knew the meaning of the donation¹². In a study in Greece establish that health care students were enthusiastic to donate and many prepare themselves to enrol but were unaware of the procedure¹³. Unlike medical professionals, British youth were in favour of donations. In a question about the desire to make a donation, our conclusion is that 8.5% of the people will donate whatever the conditions will be. The outcomes does not coincide with earlier analysis in which 33% of the licensed people wants to donate. Approximately 44.08% were not sure of accepting donations in their religious conviction, a surprising predicament and in Chennai study tinted the same issue. No religious inequality was found in Qatar study¹⁴. However, in our analysis, it was noted that Muslims (73.93%) thought that Islam did not allow donation of organs and organ donation knowledge was well among the Christian community. The kidney was the most popular organ donated (29.9%) and the eye remained behind (21.8%). This may be because

Edhi, a famous Pakistani humanitarian, donated his cornea after his death. Research in rural areas of Islamabad has shown that the kidney is the most famous organ donated. In a study by Brown et al., 57% of family members decided to donate organs to their loved ones. In our study, 57.7% of people said that donors allow donors to donate their organs when they live, but 59% say that their families should allow them in case of death. Young people in England were reluctant to donate the organs of their deceased loved ones¹⁵. Although Pakistan is a developing country, our study has shown that television is an important source of information, the same as the results of the study in Faisalabad and Islamabad. Similarly, while promoting organ donation, 57.2% chose it as in the previous study.

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